

1 **Supplementary materials 1**

2 **1. Regional distribution of the erector spinae (ES) activity when matching the reaching** 3 **distance of control participants to individuals with spinal cord injury (SCI).**

4 To investigate whether the observed differences between the controls and individuals with
5 SCI in the reaching tasks were due to their different performance, i.e., the controls reached
6 further, while the individuals with SCI reached with shorter distance, we calculated RMS
7 amplitudes and y-axis of the centroid from a portion of the forward and lateral reaching in the
8 controls so that the reaching distance was similar between the groups, and performed the
9 same statistical analysis as described in the main text.

10 A repeated-measures ANOVA demonstrated a large effect of movement phase ($F_{1,36}$
11 = 6.64, $p = 0.014$; $\eta^2p = 0.16$), and an interaction of movement phase x group ($F_{1,36} = 6.21$, p
12 = 0.017; $\eta^2p = 0.15$) on global EMG amplitude during forward reaching (SCI = 17, control =
13 21). Post-hoc analyses revealed greater global EMG amplitude during the reaching phase
14 than the returning phase in the controls ($Z = -3.50$, $p < .001$), whereas the EMG amplitude
15 was not different between the two phases of the reaching movement in the participants with
16 SCI ($Z = -.40$, $p = .69$; Supplementary figure 1A). In addition, global EMG amplitude was
17 lower in individuals with SCI than in the controls during the reaching phase ($Z = -3.48$, $p <$
18 $.001$) and during the returning phase ($Z = -2.13$, $p = .033$) of the task. For the y-axis of the
19 centroid, there was a small-to-medium effect of movement phase ($F_{1,36} = 14.73$, $p < 0.001$;
20 $\eta^2p = 0.29$) and an interaction of movement phase x group ($F_{1,36} = 11.66$, $p = 0.002$; $\eta^2p =$
21 0.25) during forward reaching. When comparing the changes in the y-axis of the centroid
22 from reaching to returning phases between participants with SCI and the controls, the
23 difference was greater in the controls (1.39cm, SD 1.32) than in the participants with SCI
24 (0.31cm, SD 0.31; $Z = -3.66$; $p < 0.001$; Supplementary figure 1B & C).

Forward reaching

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26 **Supplementary figure 1. HDEMG during forward reaching.** (A) Group data of global EMG
 27 amplitude (controls n = 21, males n = 7; SCI n = 17, males n = 14). The horizontal line within the box
 28 represents the median, and outer edges of the box the 25th and 75th percentiles. The upper and lower
 29 whiskers extend to 1.5 times the interquartile range. The red dot indicates the mean value. (B) Group
 30 data of the y-axis of the centroid (controls n = 21, males n = 7; SCI n = 17, males n = 14) for the
 31 reaching and returning phases. (C) Individual differences in the y-axis of the centroid between
 32 reaching and returning phases. * $p < 0.05$.

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34 In lateral reaching, there was no effect of movement phase ($F_{1,37} = .82, p = 0.372; \eta^2 p =$
 35 0.02), but there was an interaction of movement phase x group ($F_{1,37} = 5.00, p < 0.031; \eta^2 p =$
 36 0.12) with a small effect size on global EMG amplitude during lateral reaching (SCI = 18,
 37 control = 21; Supplementary figure 2A). When comparing the changes in the y-axis of the
 38 centroid from reaching to returning phases between participants with SCI and the controls
 39 there was a between-group difference, with the controls (1.49cm, SD 1.47) demonstrating a
 40 greater y-axis centroid difference compared to the SCI group (0.55cm, SD 0.49; $Z = -2.28; p$
 41 $= 0.022$; Supplementary figure 2B & C).

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43 **Supplementary figure 2. HDEMG of lateral reaching.** (A) Group results of global EMG amplitude
 44 (controls n = 21, males n = 7; SCI n = 18 males n = 15). The horizontal line within the box represents
 45 the median, and outer edges of the box the 25th and 75th percentiles. The upper and lower whiskers
 46 extend to 1.5 times the interquartile range. The red dot indicates the mean. (B) Group data of the y-
 47 axis of the centroid (controls n = 21, males n = 7; SCI n = 18, males n = 15) for the reaching and
 48 returning phases. (C) Individual differences of the y-axis of the centroid between reaching and
 49 returning phases. * $p < 0.05$.

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51 **2. The influence of increased thoraco-lumbar flexion on regional distribution of the**
52 **erector spinae (ES) activity during postural tasks in control participants**

53 To determine whether a more caudally distributed activation of the ES seen in individuals
54 with SCI during the rapid shoulder flexion task and during the external predicted perturbation
55 task was related to an adapted posterior pelvic tilt posture when seated. Three control
56 participants were instructed to sit with an upright posture and consequently with an increased
57 thoraco-lumbar flexion, i.e., a slouching seated posture, to simulate the posture of individuals
58 with spinal cord injury and performed the tasks as described in the methods. The heatmaps
59 and the y-axis of the centroid of these three participants were calculated and are presented
60 below. Overall, the location of the y-axis centroid remains to be in the cranial part of the ES,
61 suggesting that the change in the regional distribution of activation seen in the participants
62 with SCI was unlikely caused by their seated posture.

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64 **Supplementary figure legends**

65 **Supplementary figure 3. HDEMG of the rapid shoulder flexion task.** Differential EMG
66 amplitude maps of the ES based on the APA (left two columns) and shoulder flexion (right
67 two columns) analysis windows in rapid shoulder flexion, obtained from three able-bodied
68 participants who sat in an upright posture (left), and a slouched posture (right) to simulate the
69 posture of individuals with SCI. The deep-blue squares are removed channels after the visual
70 inspection for noisy channels. The large white circle represents the y-axis centroid, while the
71 smaller white circles represent the active channels, meaning those with an RMS amplitude
72 higher than 70% of the maximum RMS amplitude across the grid.

73 **Supplementary figure 4. HDEMG of the external perturbation task.** Differential EMG
74 amplitude maps of the ES based on the APA (left) and CPA (right) analysis windows in the

75 external perturbation task, obtained from three able-bodied participants who sat in an upright
76 posture (left two columns), and a slouched posture (right two columns) to simulate the
77 posture of individuals with SCI. The deep-blue squares are removed channels after the visual
78 inspection for noisy channels. The large white circle represents the y-axis centroid, while the
79 smaller white circles represent the active channels, meaning those with an RMS amplitude
80 higher than 70% of the maximum RMS amplitude across the grid.

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